

The Demonstration of Spontaneous Self-assembly of Novel Fluorescent Proflavin-Lipids[†]

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Fluorescent quaternary salts derived from proflavin (Pf) harbouring long alkyl chains, organize into unilamellar bilayer vesicles of diameter 22–28 nm in water and form mixed liposomes with egg lecithin lipids. The DNA binding capability of Pf-lipids and their liposome preparations have been demonstrated by fluorescence spectroscopic studies.

Lipid vesicles or liposomes formed from fluorescent precursors provide excellent probes for the investigation of several important biological surface recognition reactions^{1,2}. Additionally, they can also be used for monitoring targeted drug delivery to specific sites in the body in order to achieve tissue specific treatment of various conditions³.

The highly fluorescent and biologically compatible proflavin unit was considered a desirable precursor for crafting lipids that could undergo spontaneous self-assembly to liposomes (Fig. 1) as well as be encapsulated in bilayer membranes. We report in this communication the experimental realization of these objectives. The Pf-lipids and their liposomal preparations described herein have been examined for DNA binding interactions.

Lipids **1a-d** (Fig. 2) were prepared by treating proflavin (Pf) free base⁴, at 0°, in minimum amount of dry pyridine, with respective acyl chloride (Pf: acylchloride, molar ratio 1:3). The reaction was monitored by tlc (4–6 h) and worked up by pouring on to excess of ice-cold water, the precipitated yellow solid filtered and chromatographed on a short

Fig. 1. Spontaneous self-assembly of fluorescent proflavin-lipids.

column of silica gel with CHCl₃ and MeOH as eluents.

The bis-acylated compounds (**1a-d**) were obtained as the major products (60–80% yields) and were fully characterized by spectral (ir, ¹H nmr, uv-vis, FAB MS) and analytical data⁵. It was interesting to find that in spite of excess of acyl chloride⁶ used in each reaction, about 20% yield of monoacylated Pf-conjugates (**2a-d**) were invariably obtained. These were separated from the bis-acylated Pfs (**1a-d**) on silica gel columns and were fully characterized by spectral and analytical data⁵.

Fig. 2. Pf-lipids.

[†]Respectfully dedicated to Professor Sukh Dev on the occasion of his 75th. birthday.

Fig. 3. Electron micrograph of Pf-ol (3b) liposomes, negatively stained with uranyl acetate; 5.4 nm = 1 mm; magnification : x 182000.

Attempts to form liposomes from Pf-lipids (1a-d) were unsuccessful due to their poor solubility in water. These were subsequently transformed to their quaternary ammonium salts (3a-d) by treatment with dimethyl sulphate (neat heating with excess of reagent, at $\sim 100^\circ$, 2–4 h), evaporation *in vacuo*, and the counter anion exchange by titration with saturated KBr solution, extraction with CHCl_3 and purification on a short column of silica gel⁸.

Chloroform solution of 3a-d on evaporation to thin film followed by sonication in water afforded liposome assemblies. They stood revealed as exquisite well organized arrays when viewed under the electron microscope. A typical profile of such ensembles is shown in Fig. 3, derived from 3b. As expected, the cross-section of the liposomes were not uniform, but were in the range of 22–28 nm diameter⁹.

Fluorescence measurements (excitation 490 nm, emission 533 nm) of mixed liposomal preparation Pf-ol and egg PC lipids indicated that the Pf lipid is positioned near the head group region of the PC liposomes.

DNA binding studies were carried out with Pf-ol lipid on calf-thymus DNA (Fig. 4). Considerable increase in the fluorescence intensity with concomitant blue-shift by 10 nm of Pf emission band on addition of DNA (DNA : Pf-ol ratio 1 : 20) indicated binding of Pf to double helical DNA, presumably, in an intercalative mode¹⁰. Similar DNA binding results were obtained with mixed liposomes (SUV) of Pf-ol and egg PC lipids (molar ratio 1 : 100). Control experiments have shown that pure egg PC liposomes do not bind to DNA. The notion that Pf liposomes bind to DNA through Pf head group, perhaps, sitting on the surface of the vesicle, was supported by fluorescence quenching studies. Thus, acrylamide, which is able to quench the fluorescence of Pf-

ol lipid becomes ineffective in the presence of DNA, presumably, due to inaccessibility of the intercalated Pf head group.

The demonstrated tendency of assembly exhibited by 3a-d makes these lipids as attractive probes in diverse studies, some obvious options being, cell surface recognition, DNA

Fig. 4. Fluorescence emission (excitation 490 nm; emission 533 nm) spectra of (1) Pf-ol alone ($5 \mu\text{M}$ in phosphate buffer) and (2) Pf-ol + calf-thymus DNA (Pf-ol to DNA ratio 1 : 20).

interactions, drug targeting and redox processes¹¹. Additionally, they should serve as excellent co-surfactant in reverse micellar systems¹². Facets of these are being explored.

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- Selected data of some representative examples: **1a**: sticky solid, m/z 742 (M+H)⁺; **1c**: m.p. 200–02°, ¹H nmr δ (400 MHz; CDCl₃ + DMSO-d₆) 1.10–1.83 (16H, m), 1.93 (2H, m), 2.15 (4H, m), 2.78 (4H, m), 5.9–6.1 (2H, m), 8.05–8.20 (2H, m), 8.60–9.20 (5H, m), m/z 482 (M+H)⁺; **2b**: sticky solid, ¹H nmr δ (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆) 0.81 (3H, t), 1.25 (20H, m), 1.63 (2H, m), 1.97 (4H, m), 2.42 (2H, t), 5.28 (2H, m), 6.86 (1H, s), 7.13 (1H, d, J 8 Hz), 7.55 (1H, d, J 8 Hz), 7.95 (1H, d, J 8 Hz), 8.07 (1H, d, J 8 Hz), 8.60 (1H, s), 9.0 (1H, br s), 10.72 (1H, br s), m/z 474 (M+H)⁺; **2c**: m.p. 120–21°, m/z 346 (M+H)⁺. In their uv-vis spectra while the bisacylated Pfs (**1a-d**) exhibited only one band at 390–400 nm range (in MeOH), two bands at 390–400 and 450–456 nm range were invariably observed for the monoacylated Pfs (**2a-d**).
- Non-8-ynoic and undeca-10-ynoic acids (S. RANGANATHAN, V. MANIKTALA, RAJKUMAR and G. P. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1984, **23**, 1197) were converted into their respective acid chlorides by refluxing (2 h) with 1.5 equiv. of SOCl₂ in dry benzene.
- The free-NH₂ function in the monoacylated Pfs provides an attractive handle for linking antisense oligonucleotides (C. HELENI and J. J. TOULME, *Biochim. Biophys. Acta*, 1990, **1049**, 99) and such conjugates may be useful for studying LDL (low-density lipoprotein) receptor mediated endocytosis of antisense oligos, the advantage being that oligos can be traced in the cell because of fluorescent Pf moiety.
- Pf-lipids (**3a-d**) were obtained as sticky solids, soluble in CHCl₃ and water.
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